

Study on Seasonal Infection of Cestode Parasite in The Intestine of Gallus Gallus Domesticus from Ahmednagar District (M.S.) India

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Abstract:

In the present study, cestode parasitism and seasonal infections in Chicken from Ahmednagar were investigated. Intestine of the Chicken (i.e. Gallus gallus domesticus) were collected from various localities of Ahmednagar (Ahilyanagar) District (M.S.), India. Following dissection, the intestinal tract was examined for the presence of cestode parasites. The survey was carried out during the period of August 2020 to July 2022, at various places of Ahmednagar district. The analysis of data showed that the prevalence of cestode parasites variable according to season. The Cestode parasites recorded high prevalence in summer season of two annual cycles i.e. (70.75% and 75.11% respectively) followed by winter season (58.25% and 56.16% respectively) and low prevalence recorded in rainy season of two annual cycles (41.66% and 47.21% respectively).

Keywords: Ahmednagar District, Cestode, Gallus Gallus Domesticus, Seasonal Infections

Introduction:

Poultry are a domesticated species of birds reared for production of eggs, meat and other allied products like feathers for fancy purpose and excreta as farm manure. Even though term poultry is mostly used for chicken, it also includes other avian species like turkey, duck, guinea fowl and gees. The most popular species among poultry is chicken and it constitute about 85-90% population along with production of poultry industry in India. India is the third largest egg producer country in world (Rao, 2002). As compared to other classes of livestock for converting feed into human food, poultry ranks second in conversion efficiency in the form of enriched egg. Similarly, poultry meat ranks quite higher than beef and red meat in conversion efficiency (Jadhav and Siddiqui, 1999). In India major portion of poultry population is scattered as desi fowl population. In desi fowl control of viral

and bacterial diseases through effective vaccination and antibiotic therapy have been achieved, but no such effective vaccines were available for the parasitic disease so the losses are more often due to the parasitism. The enteric diseases are important in poultry industry in recent years because these diseases cause enormous loss by way of high mortality, decreased production and low meat quality (Deb et.al. 1986). Among the enteric diseases helminthiasis has taken due attention of poultry farmers on account of decreased weight gain and egg production (Rehman, 1958). Due to heavy infection of cestodes particularly in young folks are responsible for high degree of mortality and in older fowls for poor growth and lowered production from insidiously debilitating, but generally unrecognized condition (Nath and Pande, 1963). Hence the enteric disease caused by

helminthes specially cestodes causes heavy mortality and decreased in nutritional value of poultry product. In the rural areas mostly chicken are kept in free range scavenging system. In this system birds are allowed to move around freely in the surroundings areas of the houses during day time, searching for food, which mainly consists of house hold wastes, insect larvae and seeds. Due to scavenging habit the birds are at high risk to all type of infections, particularly gastrointestinal parasitic infections. The chicken infected with cestode parasite shows retarded growth, decreased egg production, reduced weight gain, granuloma formation in duodenum, desquamation of villi and sub mucosal gland congestion, inflammatory reaction and vacuolation of epithelial cells (Kurkure et.al., 1998)

Considerable work has been done on the cestode parasite of chicken. So keeping in view the importance of cestode parasite in chicken, the present study was designed to investigate prevalence of cestode parasite of domestic fowl (*Gallus gallus domesticus*) in Ahmednagar district.

Material and Method:

The survey was carried out during the period of August 2020 to July 2022, at various places of Ahmednagar district Viz. Ahmednagar city, Shrirampur, Shrigonda, Shevgaon,

Sangamner, Rahata, Rahuri, Kopergaon, Nevasa, Parner, Pathardi, Karjat and Jamkhed. The gastrointestinal tract of *Gallus gallus domesticus* examined in two years, for cestode parasites. The gastrointestinal tracts were carefully examined. According to the present study the survey conducted only on the prevalence of cestode. Cestodes were collected and a complete data of collection recorded about the infected host and parasites is summarised. The Cestode parasites were flattened and kept in 4% formalin, dehydrated in ascending grades of alcohols, stained with Aceto carmine, cleared with xylene and mounted in DPX.

Then level of parasite infection was calculated monthly as well as seasonally by using prevalence formula as per Margolis et al. and Bhure et al.

$$\text{Prevalence of Infection} = \frac{\text{Total number of hosts infected}}{\text{Total number of hosts examined}} \times 100.$$

Result and Discussion:

The data of prevalence of cestode parasites are found in *Gallus gallus domesticus* in Ahmednagar district (M.S) India during the period of August 2020 to July 2022. The prevalence or incidences of infection of cestode parasites were calculated in Table no.1.

Table No. 1: Seasonal prevalence of Cestodes from *Gallus gallus domesticus*, during the year August 2020 to July 2022 from Ahmednagar district.

Sr. No.	Month	No of host examined	No. of host infected	No. of parasite collected	Prevalence %
1	Aug 2020	25	10	18	40%
2	Sept 2020	15	08	15	53.33%
3	Oct 2020	08	06	13	75%
4	Nov 2020	15	09	13	60%
5	Dec 2020	25	12	15	48%
6	Jan 2021	18	09	12	50%
7	Feb 2021	20	15	20	75%
8	Mar 2021	18	13	15	72%
9	Apr 2021	20	14	22	70%

10	May 2021	18	12	20	66%
11	Jun 2021	15	06	08	40%
12	Jul 2021	12	04	10	33.33%
13	Aug 2021	19	07	10	36.84%
14	Sept 2021	15	06	09	40%
15	Oct 2021	23	15	18	65.21%
16	Nov 2021	18	08	07	44.44%
17	Dec 2021	20	10	09	50%
18	Jan 2022	20	13	13	65%
19	Feb 2022	17	13	12	76.47%
20	Mar 2022	25	16	20	64%
21	Apr 2022	20	14	15	70%
22	May 2022	10	09	16	90%
23	Jun 2022	25	13	13	52%
24	Jul 2022	15	09	10	60%

Graph No.1: Prevalence of Cestode Parasite from intestine of Gallus gallus domesticus during August 2020 to July 2022 from Ahmednagar district.

Table No 2: Seasonal fluctuation of Cestode Parasite in host Gallus gallus domesticus during August 2020 to July 2022 from Ahmednagar district.

Parasite	Seasons	Prevalence% Aug 2020- Jul 2021	Prevalence% Aug 2021 – Jul 2022
Cestode parasite	Rainy	41.66%	47.21%
	Winter	58.25%	56.16%
	Summer	70.75%	75.11%

Graph No 2: Seasonal fluctuation of Cestode Parasite in host Gallus gallus domesticus during August 2020 to July 2022 from Ahmednagar district.

The analysis of data showed that the prevalence of cestode parasites variable according to season. The Cestode parasites recorded high prevalence in summer season of two annual cycles i.e. (70.75% and 75.11% respectively) followed by winter season (58.25% and 56.16% respectively) and low prevalence recorded in rainy season of two annual cycles (41.66% and 47.21% respectively).

The results of the present study showed a variable prevalence of cestode parasite in *Gallus gallus domesticus* in Ahmednagar district. It might be due the scavenging habit of the birds and changes in the environment in the study area. The observed mean intensity of worms in the alimentary canal of infected birds might be due to consumption of infested droppings or infested intermediate hosts of parasites such as beetles, cockroaches, earthworms, flies and grasshoppers in poorly managed stocks (Abdul, 1987).

The same report done by (Suhail Rashid, Syed Tanveer and ShaziaAhad 2017) in domestic fowl of Kashmir valley with annual seasonal sex based and weight based prevalence. In Egypt Shahin,(2011), recorded Cestodes were varied in accordance to breeding season. Similarly Matur, (2010) reported that *Raillietina echinobothrida* and *Raillietina tetragona* were recovered from both local and exotic breeds with a percentage prevalence of 19.0% and 22.2% respectively. Achaich. N and N Vijaya Kumar, (2013) studied seasonal prevalence of *Raillietina tetragona* in domestic fowl from Warangal region of Andhra Pradesh. Naphade S.T, (2013) examines a survey on prevalence of helminth infection in Desi poultry birds from Marathwada region of Maharashtra. Similar work done by Jadhav and Bhure, (2006), and reported high temperature, low rainfall and sufficient moisture are necessary for development of parasite. Hence high

prevalence occurs in summer followed by other seasons.

Conclusion:

Cestode parasite infection in *Gallus gallus domesticus* is positively associated with the seasons of summer, winter and rainy season. The Cestode parasites recorded high prevalence in summer season followed by winter season and low prevalence recorded in rainy season. Furthermore, this result is helpful for further research on the impact of cestode parasites on chicken health and biochemistry and contributes to awareness among consumer.

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